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ETHICAL IMPERATIVES FOR THE USE OF AI IN DEFENSE: INSIGHTS FROM AN INTERSECTORAL CONFERENCE.

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October 5th, 2024.

Policy Statement

Integrating artificial intelligence (AI) into military operations presents opportunities and ethical challenges. As AI becomes increasingly integral to defense strategies, ensuring its deployment aligns with humanitarian values and international law is essential. The increasing autonomy and decision-making power of AI systems in military contexts necessitates a robust ethical framework to ensure these technologies are deployed responsibly and in accordance with humanitarian principles. This policy brief explores some perspectives on the ethical challenges associated with using AI in defense, presented at an intersection event promoted in partnership between academic and private entities.

Background

Pursuing military objectives has historically served as a significant impetus for much of the research and development that has resulted in the present-day prevalence of multifunctional technologies. The Internet, arguably the most prominent example, emerged from initiatives to enhance communication and information sharing for defense purposes. Another pivotal milestone in technological innovation was the advancement of cybernetics, which sought to develop predictive machines for implementation in anti-aircraft targeting. Likewise, investment in creating a machine capable of playing chess has provided foundational support for the evolution of more sophisticated artificial intelligence (AI) applications.

As AI continues to evolve and its potential applications in the defense sector expand, it is crucial to address the ethical implications of its use. The 2024 Paris Conference on Digital and AI Ethics, sponsored by Datadog, Inria, Quintessence AI, Meta, Google, and Orange, brought together academics, practitioners, and industry leaders. The event united academics, practitioners, and industry leaders. One of the essential tracks, "AI for Defense Strategies and Law Enforcement," explored the transformative impact of AI on military operations and highlighted the need for ethical considerations in its deployment.

Findings

The conference's presentations and discussions examined AI's transformative potential in defense, the complexities of cyber espionage, the role of AI in digital enforcement, and the challenges of maintaining digital sovereignty. The contentious issue of autonomous weapons systems (AWS) was explored, revealing significant concerns regarding human oversight and accountability. These insights provide a comprehensive overview of the current state of AI in the military sector and form the basis for subsequent policy recommendations.

Cyber Espionage and Legal Frameworks: The use of artificial intelligence in cyber espionage signifies a substantial transformation in contemporary warfare. AI-enabled cyber operations add complexity to the legal landscape, as existing international laws, including the Tallinn Manual, provide insufficient guidance in regulating espionage activities. Although international laws, notably the Tallinn Manual, give some insights regarding cyber operations, a significant gap persists within the legal framework.

Data Sovereignty: Another potential threat to sovereignty is the military use of cloud technology. Authoritarian countries have expressed their willingness to control data flow through their territories. Furthermore, state dependency on American providers poses challenges to managing sensitive data since the US Cloud Act requires American providers to share data upon request, regardless of the nationality of the data owner (2).

Making sense of data: AI is a crucial tool for generating intelligence from the overwhelming influx of data from drones, satellites, and other sources on the battlefield. AI-driven systems rapidly analyze this vast information, identifying patterns and potential threats with unprecedented speed and accuracy. This capability grants a significant strategic advantage to those who can process and interpret this data faster, ensuring real-time situational awareness and informed decision-making. (6)

One problem is hallucinations, a byproduct of AI. To address unreliability in the defense context, possible solutions include ontology-augmented generation, which involves training models on more reliable data to enhance the accuracy and reliability of AI systems.

Context specificity is also vital to achieving ethical standards, as a one-size-fits-all approach does not work in military applications due to the varying nature of threats and operational environments. (4) Lastly, ethical product design should involve an interdisciplinary team, ensuring a diversity of backgrounds and points of view (5).

Autonomous Weapons Systems (AWS): Autonomous weapons systems, which can select and engage targets without human intervention, represent one of the most contentious aspects of AI in the military, raising profound ethical and legal concerns. As former NATO Supreme Allied Commander General Jean-Paul Paloméros put it, AI tools can aid in simulations and scenario testing, significantly improving strategic planning and operational efficiency. However, full targeting automation and critical decision-making processes, such as target selection, should be avoided (3). AI has the potential to enhance decision-making processes in defense operations by providing augmented intelligence, but ensuring human oversight is crucial to maintaining accountability and minimizing collateral damage.

Private sector representatives agree with the assessment: AI allows for a better-informed human decision but should be kept under “meaningful human control,” complying with the rules of distinction and proportionality in International Humanitarian Law. AI should be used to augment human decision-making, not replace it. They also suggest creating an implementation guide, where the debate around “autonomy” shifts into the more concrete issue of “confidence” instead. (4)

Recommendations

The following recommendations include selected insights from the various presentations and statements given by conference speakers regarding the ethical use of AI in defense. We have also included recommendations from previous research developed by the InterAgency Institute. (7)

- **Create a Legally Binding International Treaty:** Enforce a legal ban on autonomous weapon systems possessing anti-personnel capabilities, specifically those that can autonomously perform critical functions such as targeting and discharging firearms. This measure aims to uphold human oversight and avert potential misuse. As advocated by the United Nations and the International Committee of the Red Cross, the treaty, projected to be established by 2026, should explicitly delineate acceptable and impermissible applications of artificial intelligence in military operations.

- **Develop Implementation Guidance for AWS:** Create a detailed implementation guide for Autonomous Weapons Systems (AWS) that ensures adherence to International Humanitarian Law (IHL). This guide should emphasize maintaining “meaningful human control” over crucial decision-making processes, particularly in target selection, to comply with the principles of distinction and proportionality.
- **Foster Multidisciplinary Collaboration:** Engage experts from diverse disciplines, such as law, ethics, technology, and military strategy, to address the complex challenges that artificial intelligence presents within the defense realm.
- **Implement Rigorous Testing Protocols:** Establish mandatory, comprehensive testing and validation protocols for artificial intelligence systems before deployment to ensure their reliability, safety, and compliance with ethical standards.
- **Create an AI Ethics Board:** Form an independent oversight committee consisting of experts in AI, military strategy, ethics, and international law to review and assess AI applications in military operations continuously.
- **Conduct Regular Ethical Audits:** Perform regular, independent ethical audits of artificial intelligence systems used in military operations to ensure adherence to international humanitarian law and safeguard human rights.
- **Augment AI Training with Reliable Data:** To address the issue of AI “hallucinations,” implement ontology-augmented generation techniques, which use highly reliable data to train AI systems. This approach will improve the accuracy and dependability of AI in defense contexts.
- **Enhance and Expand International Cyber Laws:** Advocate for developing and adopting an expanded international legal framework specifically addressing AI-enabled cyber espionage. This framework should build on existing guidelines, such as the Tallinn Manual, to provide clear, enforceable regulations and definitions that cover the complexities introduced by AI in cyber operations.
- **Strengthen National Data Sovereignty Policies:** Implement robust national policies to ensure data sovereignty, particularly in the context of military and defense data. These policies should include measures to safeguard sensitive data

stored in the cloud, limiting reliance on foreign cloud service providers and reducing vulnerability to foreign government data requests under laws such as the U.S. Cloud Act.

Final Considerations

Integrating artificial intelligence into military operations necessitates a careful balance between the adoption of technological advancements and the adherence to ethical principles. While artificial intelligence offers significant efficiency, accuracy, and strategic advantages, these benefits must not be pursued at the expense of human oversight and accountability.

The potential risks associated with autonomous weapons systems, in particular, mandate rigorous ethical scrutiny and the establishment of robust legal frameworks to ensure their utilization aligns with international humanitarian standards. There is a pressing need for global, interdisciplinary, and interagency collaboration to develop comprehensive legal standards – including an international treaty – that regulate the deployment of artificial intelligence in warfare, ensuring that its application respects human rights and adheres to international humanitarian law.

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